

An Overview of The Optimisation of 3D Printed Concrete Using Silica Sand

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ABSTRACT

3D Printing is an additive manufacturing process. 3D concrete printing is an innovative construction technique that uses computer-controlled machines to create structures layer by layer. This method allows for intricate designs and shapes to be produced with precision. The process is efficient and can reduce material waste, making it a sustainable option for construction projects. It doesn't require the use of formwork and also requires less labour. Silica sand is a waste product of the foundry and paint industry. It is known for its uniform particle size, which can result in a more consistent and even finish in construction projects. Additionally, silica sand is free of impurities like clay and organic matter, making it ideal for use in manufacturing high-quality concrete and mortar. Its angular shape also provides better bonding properties, improving the overall strength and durability of the construction material. It can be a viable alternative to river sand in the production of concrete. Our project deals with the use and optimization of silica sand as an alternative to river sand in the production of 3D Printed Concrete.

Keywords: Silica sand-based 3D printing, Additive manufacturing in construction, Binder jetting with silica sand, Sand-based additive manufacturing, 3D printing for sustainable construction, 3D printing with sand, Silica sand in digital fabrication, Construction-scale 3D printing Natural materials in 3D printing

INTRODUCTION

3D Printed concrete (3DPC) is a new technology in the construction industry serving lots of purposes. To address the challenges like labour shortage, increased structural complexity & low efficiency in building construction with present practices and looking at present need of technology, and to overcome it; 3D Printed Concrete is necessary. The field of 3D concrete printing has witnessed significant advancements in recent years. In this project, we explore the utilisation of silica sand as a key material for 3D printing. Silica sand, known for its fine particle size and excellent binding properties, offers exciting possibilities for sustainable construction. When compared to traditional construction technology, additive manufacturing, also known as three-dimensional printing (3DP), offers the benefits of high building efficiency, low labour cost, and reduced construction waste. 3D printed concrete may be poured layer by layer with a 3D printer instead of utilising formwork or a vibration technique. Its key

performance indicators, including workability, setting, and hardening time, and mechanical qualities, may be improved by material selection and printing settings.

3D-Printing Concrete Technology

The technology known as 3D-printed concrete utilises 3D printing to manufacture concrete components. This innovative process involves using specialised software to control the extrusion mechanism, which feeds a designed concrete slurry according to predetermined specifications. By utilising a nozzle and a well-designed printing program, the desired concrete elements are extruded, effectively integrating computer-aided design tools into the construction process. This novel approach, often referred to as mould less moulding technology, offers the ability to construct complex structures with reduced energy consumption compared to traditional methods. Additionally, it allows for customised structures tailored to the specific requirements of each project. The widespread adoption and promotion of

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3D-printed concrete technology have the potential to significantly reduce In 2012, ETH Zurich initiated the mesh mould project to explore the potential of digitally producing concrete structures with intricate geometric complexity. This method involves constructing a polymer network using 3D printing and selecting the appropriate particle size aggregate to design a concrete mix ratio and preserve the concrete by blocking the mesh. In 2015, ETH Zurich's Lloret et al. introduced fast sliding mould technology, known as smart dynamics casting (SDC). This method allows for the creation of a sliding mould around a steel bar, improving the structural integrity of the printed components In 2019, a groundbreaking project called "In-situ 3D-printing double-layer demonstration buildings" was launched by China Construction Second Bureau South China Company and China Construction Industrial Tech Research Institution Co., Limited. This initiative aims to print buildings on-site using 3D printing technology. Figure 1.2 [5] depicts the evolution of 3D printing technology for building with cement-based materials. Over the past 20 years, research and application have

propelled 3D-printing cementitious technology forward, offering advantages such as rapid construction, topology optimization, high mechanisation individualised customization, detailed structural building construction, and unique architectural designs. The industry has experienced significant growth, driven by the development of new technologies, materials, and various technical applications. 3D Printing has a potential to revolutionise the construction industry. It seems to be very promising. It can decrease the need for unskilled/skilled labour, formwork. This is going to decrease the cost of construction. Innovations in this industry can help a lot to everyone. Lower cost and faster construction will benefit both the constructors as well as the people who will end up using the structure. There is a possibility that this research will shed light towards a path that will help us in this process. Thus, this project seems to be heavily beneficial to the construction industry Following are the various steps that we decided to use for the successful conduction of our project. The steps are mentioned in detail below.

Chart 3.1 Flowchart of methodology for project

To decide what material to focus our study on, firstly we had to see the various studies that were conducted on different materials in the context of 3d Printing. Then we had to see what materials looked promising. If there was a material that had been heavily studied, we may not have been able to contribute to the research process. Hence, we looked for materials that

had little research done, but the research was promising. Various materials related that were used as admixtures, replacements to cement, replacements to aggregate, etc. were studied. Based on the materials that we studied, we had decided to focus our research on silica sand. This is a by-product of the paint and foundry industry. It is a renewable resource. It can be

used as a replacement for river sand which is a non-renewable resource. In certain research papers, we have found out that replacement of sand in certain proportions increases the compressive strength of the concrete, as well as the fresh concrete properties such as setting time, flowability, pumpability, etc. Thus, we have chosen to focus our research on the optimization of silica sand. Based on the materials that we studied, we had decided to focus our research on silica sand. This is a by-product of the paint and foundry industry. It is a renewable resource. It can be used as a replacement for river sand which is a non-renewable resource. In certain research papers, we have found out that replacement of sand in certain proportions increases the compressive strength of the concrete, as well as the fresh concrete properties such as setting time, flowability, pump ability, etc. Thus, we have chosen to focus our research on the optimisation of silica sand.

CONCLUSION:

From our work on this project, we were able to draw some key insights in the topic. The first one was that silica sand is a viable alternative to river sand. 50% replacement of river sand by silica sand yields the highest compressive, tensile and flexural strength. Thus 50% replacement is optimum for 3d printing. The results of tests were satisfying.

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